

Coon and Tucker "Cattle are more motivated for a high-concentrate diet than Sudan grass hay despite low reticulorumen pH"

Supplemental Table S1. Effect of interacting with an aversive electrified barrier to access 4 L of either SG or TMR* on behaviours in finishing cattle fed a high-concentrate diet for current periods** -3 to 0

Variable	ANOVA (Type III SS)								
	DF***	Treatment chisq	p-value	DF***	Current relative to MPP chisq	p-value	DF***	Interaction chisq	p-value
RIC registered visits	1	10.87	<0.01	1	2.71	0.1	1	0.46	0.5
Confident visits	1	13.70	<0.01	1	2.96	0.09	1	1.11	0.29
Unsuccessful attempts	1	0.97	0.32	1	0.04	0.84	1	0.42	0.52
% Intake	1	23.52	<0.01	1	0.65	0.42	1	1.00	0.32

*SG: 4 L or 200 g of Sudan grass hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=9), TMR: 4 L or ~2 kg of a total mixed ration (11% roughage; n=12)

**Periods were 24-h intervals during which the current applied to the electrified barrier remained constant.

***Numerator DF obtained from the ANOVA type III SS are presented; denominator DF are known to be erroneous in many mixed models and are not presented (e.g. <https://stat.ethz.ch/pipermail/r-help/2006-May/094765.html>)

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Supplemental Table S2. Back-transformed means and SE for models analyzing the effect of interacting with an aversive electrified barrier to access 4 L of either SG or TMR* on behaviours in finishing cattle fed a high-concentrate diet for current periods** -3 to 0

Variable	Treatment							
	SG				TMR			
	Mean	SE	Lower confidence limit	Upper confidence limit	Mean	SE	Lower confidence limit	Upper confidence limit
RIC registered visits	2.40	0.44	1.68	3.43	5.33	0.58	4.30	6.59
Confident visits	2.07	0.35	1.49	2.88	4.72	0.44	3.92	5.67
Unsuccessful attempts	0.68	0.28	0.31	1.50	0.91	0.28	0.50	1.66
% Intake	31.80	5.22	22.50	42.80	73.70	3.66	66.00	80.30

*SG: 4 L or 200 g of Sudan grass hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=9), TMR: 4 L or ~2kg of a total mixed ration (11% roughage; n=12)

**Periods were 24-h intervals during which the current applied to the electrified barrier remained constant.